

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Swasthasya Swasthya Raksanam: Siddhantic Approach to Preventive Healthcare in Ayurveda

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 11 Aug 2025

Keywords:

Swasthya Raksanam,
Preventive healthcare,
Maulik Siddhanta,
Ayurveda, Dincharya,
Ritucharya, Sadvritta,
Prakrti, Agni, Ojas,
Rasayana, Lifestyle
disorders, public health,
Kriyakala

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.16793277

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, lays strong emphasis on the preservation of health through the principle of "Swasthasya Swasthya Raksanam"—maintaining the health of the healthy. Unlike modern systems that primarily focus on disease treatment, Ayurveda prioritizes preventive care through daily and seasonal regimens, proper diet, ethical conduct, and mind-body balance. This article explores the foundational Ayurvedic concepts (Maulik Siddhanta) that support preventive healthcare, such as Tridosha, Prakrti, Agni, and Srotas, and how practices like Dincharya, Ritucharya, Sadvritta, and Rasayana contribute to strengthening immunity and promoting overall well-being. In the context of rising lifestyle disorders, adopting these time-tested guidelines offers a sustainable approach to public health and disease prevention.

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, the foremost aim is described as:

स्वस्थस्य स्वास्थ्य रक्षणं आतुरस्य विकार प्रशमनम्
च। (चरक संहिता, सूत्रस्थान ३०/२६)

This aphorism establishes that the primary aim of *Ayurveda* is not just to cure disease, but to

maintain the health of the healthy. In this way, *Ayurveda* distinguishes itself as a preventive science long before the concept gained prominence in modern medicine. Health in *Ayurveda* is defined as a harmonious state of *dosas* (*Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*), *Agni* (digestive/metabolic fire), *Dhatu*s (tissues), *Malas* (waste), along with a balanced mind, senses, and soul. This dynamic balance is influenced by an individual's *Prakrti*

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

(constitution), daily regimen (*Dincharya*), seasonal regimen (*Ritucharya*), dietary habits (*Ahara*), and mental discipline (*Sadvritta*). In the face of rising lifestyle-related disorders, the *Ayurvedic* focus on preventive healthcare becomes even more relevant. Through its *Maulik Siddhantas*, *Ayurveda* offers holistic, sustainable strategies to protect and promote health. These ancient principles guide individuals to live in tune with nature and their own constitution, minimizing the risk of disease and enhancing longevity and vitality.

DISCUSSION

1. *Maulik Siddhant* Behind *Swasthya Raksanam*

***Tridosha Siddhanta*:** Balancing *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* is central to prevention.

- 1) ***Panchmahabhuta Siddhant*:** Ensures compatibility of diet and environment with the body.
- 2) ***Prakrti Siddhanta*:** Helps in planning individual-specific preventive regimens.
- 3) ***Agni Siddhanta*:** Maintaining digestive fire is key to disease prevention.
- 4) ***Rasa-Virya-Vipaka Siddhanta*:** Used to choose preventive herbs and diet.

2. *Dincharya* (Daily Regimen)

Daily practices like *Abhyanga* (oil massage), *Nasya* (nasal cleansing), *Dhantadhavana* (oral care), and *Vyayama* (exercise) enhance immunity, regulate metabolism, and improve mental clarity.

3. *Ritucharya* (Seasonal Regimen)

Seasonal changes cause fluctuations in *dosas*. *Ayurveda* prescribes dietary and behavioral changes to maintain balance throughout the

seasons (e.g., light diet in *Grishma*, oily and heavy in *Hemanta*).

4. *Ahara-Vihara* (Diet and Lifestyle)

Ayurveda emphasizes *Satmya Ahara* (wholesome food), *Matra-Ahara* (quantitative eating), and *Asana Vidhi* (eating discipline) to keep the digestive system and metabolism in balance.

5. *Sadvritta* (Code of Conduct)

Mental and emotional health is sustained through ethical behavior, compassion, truthfulness, and self-control, ensuring psychosomatic balance.

6. *Rasayana* (Rejuvenation Therapy)

Rasayana is not only curative but preventive — it enhances *Ojas*, the essence responsible for immunity and vitality. *Chyavanprasa* is a classic example.

7. *Nidana Parivarjana* (Avoidance of Causative Factors)

Prevention includes knowledge of *Hetu* (causes) and actively avoiding exposure to them.

8. *Vyadhi Utpatti* and *Kriyakala*

Understanding *Kriyakala* (six stages of disease development) allows for timely interventions before the disease manifests.

CONCLUSION

The *Ayurvedic* principle of "*Swasthasya Swasthya Raksanam*" reflects a proactive and holistic vision of healthcare that emphasizes preservation over intervention. Rooted in the *Maulik Siddhantas*, this approach integrates balanced living through diet (*Ahara*), daily routine (*Dincharya*), seasonal adaptation (*Ritucharya*), ethical conduct (*Sadvritta*), and rejuvenation (*Rasayana*). In

today's world, where lifestyle-related diseases are increasingly common, *Ayurveda* offers timeless tools for maintaining health, enhancing immunity, and preventing the onset of disease. The integration of these preventive measures into modern life not only reduces disease burden but also supports physical, mental, and spiritual well-being. Therefore, adopting *Ayurveda's* preventive healthcare principles can play a significant role in shaping a sustainable, individualized, and holistic public health model for the future.

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HOW TO CITE: Dr. Anupam Sheoran*, Dr. Imran Patel, Swasthasya Swasthya Raksanam: Siddhantic Approach to Preventive Healthcare in Ayurveda, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 8, 1018-1020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16793277>

